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REVIEW REPORT

OPTIMIZED PRODUCTION SCHEME FOR ^{225}Ac

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Abstract:

^{225}Ac is an alpha particle emitting isotope that has attracted worldwide attention from the nuclear medicine community for its potential as a therapeutic agent in targeted alpha therapy. It decays with a half life of 9.920(2) days, making it long-lived enough to be produced, separated, shipped and labeled in a reasonable time, while still being well matched to biological half-lives of targeting vectors. While under intense (pre)-clinical research, one of the major bottlenecks in this research is global supply. In an effort to produce more ^{225}Ac , a number of production pathways are considered, including various irradiation modes on ^{226}Ra targets as well as high energy proton spallation of natural thorium or uranium based targets. Each mode of irradiation co-produces other radioactive species which must then be efficiently separated in order to recover ^{225}Ac with high radioisotopic purity and yield. Only then can ^{225}Ac be processed into a radiopharmaceutical which conforms to purity standards set by pharmacopeia regulations. In this report, a critical analysis of current and developing production and separation techniques is provided. In light of the findings of the review, an optimized production and purification pathway is recommended.

LISA ITN, 2020

For more information on the project, partners and contributors please see: lisa-itn.web.cern.ch

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Executive Summary:

Introduction

^{225}Ac is a promising medical radioisotope for the treatment of distributed and metastatic cancer.

The bottleneck in pursuing (pre) clinical ^{225}Ac -based cancer treatment is the isotope supply.

An overview of current production methods is given, along with recommendations of separation methods, subject to results of ongoing experiments.

Current ^{225}Ac supply

Almost all of the 70 GBq ^{225}Ac produced annually comes from ^{229}Th generators.

Laboratories in North America are increasing the annual supply through high energy proton spallation of thorium.

Promising production pathways

^{226}Ra targets can be irradiated using electron, deuteron or low energy proton accelerators. The irradiation of ^{226}Ra with low energy protons is the most efficient production method with respect to beam power and target material quantity. These irradiations could be performed at facilities with 14+ MeV proton accelerators. The main limitation is the radio protection hazard of the active target materials including the gaseous ^{222}Rn alpha decay daughter of ^{226}Ra .

^{229}Th generator stock could be increased through either reactor irradiation of ^{230}Th or photo-nuclear reactions of $^{\text{nat}}\text{Th}$. Though inefficient, these methods contribute to strategic semi-permanent ^{225}Ac generators.

High energy proton spallation of Th-based targets produce ^{225}Ac with medium efficiency. Due to the high-energy of the proton beams used, the method can be scaled by increasing target thicknesses. Appropriate radioactive material handling facilities must be installed.

Separation

Proton spallation of $^{\text{nat}}\text{Th}$ leads to co-production of contaminants, notably ^{225}Ra and ^{227}Ac .

Radiochemical separation of irradiated targets can be performed to recover a solution of ^{225}Ac containing ^{227}Ac at typically 0.15% by activity. ^{225}Ra can also be recovered for use as a ^{225}Ac generator with negligible ^{227}Ac .

Another purification technique is the use of resonance laser ionization and mass separation. ^{225}Ac has been recovered with an efficiency of < 10%, but with a ^{227}Ac suppression factor of approximately 6000.

Resonant ionization and mass separation can also be performed on ^{225}Ac samples recovered from radiochemical separation. It has been demonstrated that ^{225}Ac can be recovered more efficiently (approximately 10% efficient) when deposited on a rhenium foil compared to when separated from bulk irradiated target. Further experiments are required to confirm this.

Ideal separation approach for spallation produced ^{225}Ac

The current optimized separation method to obtain the most ^{225}Ac subject to a maximum ^{227}Ac amount of 0.01% by activity comprises radiochemical separation of an irradiated target followed by resonant laser ionization and mass separation of the recovered Ac eluate. The ^{225}Ra fraction in this approach should be kept as an ^{225}Ac generator.

For production of ^{225}Ac as a ^{213}Bi generator, radiochemical separation only is the optimum method to obtain the most ^{213}Bi with requisite purity.

Ongoing developments are being performed in order to improve the current 10% separation efficiency limitation. For example, studies are in progress to develop high-throughput ion sources, along with molecular beam operation well-suited to ^{225}Ac collection, and the development of an actinium laser ionization scheme with better efficiency.

Further experiments are required to confirm the above conclusions that have been drawn from a limited body of work.

Outlook

In the future, a consortium of facilities and organisations with expertise in the different production and separation methods should be established to co-ordinate a unified approach to ^{225}Ac production for medical purposes.

1 Introduction

In 1999, the first instance of using an alpha emitter in targeted radio-nuclide therapy was reported [1]. Observations have shown that the 60-100 μm path length of alpha particles in biological media, along with their high linear energy transfer lead to a selective and potent treatment. Since then, the effect of alpha radiation on biological media has been studied more intensely in-silico[2, 3], in-vitro [4, 5, 6], in-vivo using rodent models or in humans in compassionate use scenarios[7, 8, 9, 10, 11], and in-vivo in phase I and II human trials[12, 13, 14]. Multiple review articles and references therein cover these developments in further detail[15, 16, 17, 18], while information on ongoing clinical trials can be found on www.clinicaltrials.gov.

The results of these numerous studies point towards the general potency of α -emitters for the treatment of distributed or metastatic cancers. The α -particles cause cell death through a number of physically, chemically and biologically mediated responses that is outlined in a review by Pouget et al. [18]. Alpha emitting isotopes can treat selectively and potently only when they are directed towards the target tumor site by means of a biological vector molecule. Such vectors may be antibodies, antibody fragments, hormones, hormone analogues, peptides or any molecule with a specific affinity for over-expressed receptors on tumor cell surfaces. The radio-isotope must therefore be bound to the vectors by means of bifunctional chelators. The bound combination of α -emitter, chelator and targeting molecule is known as the radiopharmaceutical. In order for the radiopharmaceutical to be of clinical use, it must be shown to be reliably stable, and to limit non-targeted cytotoxicity. It is also desirable that the α -emitter used should have a half-life that is matched to the biological half-life of the vector molecule, and that contaminant species labelled to the vector molecule remain below acceptable limits. At the same time, the targeted cytotoxicity should be maximised, which can be accomplished with high effective dose per unit activity. With these considerations, ^{225}Ac has emerged as one of the leading candidates for an α -emitting radiopharmaceutical. Its clinical potential came to global attention in 2016, when a compassionate use treatment of two patients with terminal stage prostate cancer showed remarkable results [11]. Subsequently, many phase 1 clinical trials have begun to further investigate ^{225}Ac -labelled pharmaceuticals, supported by the

growth of pharmaceutical companies with dedicated focus on ^{225}Ac -based pharmaceutical development (actinium pharmaceuticals inc., fusion pharmaceuticals inc., AlfaRim, etc.). Despite the intensifying worldwide effort to study ^{225}Ac as a medical isotope, the main limitation to further developments remains the global supply of ^{225}Ac .

The aim of this report is to provide a comparative overview of current and emerging production pathways and their potential for global supply. Special attention is then given to the method of high energy proton bombardment of U- or Th- based targets. Different separation methods to recover isotopically pure ^{225}Ac from this irradiation method are evaluated. An optimum separation method is then proposed based on the findings from radiochemical separation experiments performed at TRIUMF and laser ionization and mass separation (LIMS) experiments performed at CERN MEDICIS. The results and proposals of this report are subject to confirmation from ongoing experiments.

2 Current ^{225}Ac supply

Currently, almost all ^{225}Ac supplied to (pre)-clinical research groups worldwide is provided by existing ^{229}Th generators, which were themselves recovered from stockpiled ^{233}U . It is estimated that 70 GBq is eluted worldwide from a combination of generators in the USA, Germany and Russia. Other generators exist in Canada and Belgium. The scale of these generators cannot meaningfully contribute to global supply, however remain useful for research.

Other than ^{229}Th generators, ^{225}Ac is currently supplied for pre-clinical trials by the tri-lab effort composed of Brookhaven, Oak Ridge and Los Alamos national laboratories. This collaboration leverages the proton accelerators of Brookhaven and Los Alamos to irradiate Thorium foils. ^{225}Ac is then separated using radiochemistry at Oak Ridge laboratories. In 2020, the Food and Drugs Administration (FDA) of the United States of America accepted a drug master file submission for such accelerator produced ^{225}Ac from the tri-lab effort. At TRIUMF in Canada, a similar approach is employed. Stacks of natural Thorium are irradiated monthly or bi-monthly. The foils are processed by radiochemistry in order to obtain aqueous ^{225}Ac solutions that can then be shipped for pre-clinical research. ^{225}Ac of two different purity grades can be obtained by this method, with more details given in subsection 4.1.2. The authors are not aware of any further reliable accelerator-based suppliers. Therefore the totality of ^{225}Ac supply depends on only these few laboratories that operate a ^{229}Th generator or have the capacity to regularly irradiate thorium foils. While the accelerator produced ^{225}Ac from the tri-lab effort and from TRIUMF promises to greatly improve the ^{225}Ac available annually, it is still insufficient to meet global demand. Furthermore, the fact that these efforts have the greatest traction in North America means that ^{225}Ac availability in Europe or other regions of the world may be limited, or unfavoured.

3 Promising production pathways

The global supply of ^{225}Ac could be greatly increased by leveraging facilities capable of annually producing samples with activities of the order of magnitude of 1 GBq or greater through a number of production pathways. An overview of these main production pathways based on a literature review is presented in Table 1. The production rates normalised to driver beam intensity and target mass, along with the main co-produced radioactive species that may be present after separation are shown. Methods for isolation of ^{225}Ac , ^{225}Ra or ^{229}Th are suggested based on what has been performed in the references studies, or what is envisaged. Finally, non-exhaustive examples of facilities that could leverage such production means is provided. Note that any facility with the driver mentioned could potentially contribute to ^{225}Ac production.

In this section, the production pathways in Table 1 are further discussed and compared with respect to their production efficiency, scaling potential, and limitations. Full technical details of the methods are beyond the scope of this report, but can be reviewed through the corresponding references.

Table 1: Overview of current and projected production routes of ^{225}Ac .

Reaction	Production rate [MBq μAh^{-1} g^{-1}]		Important radioactive contaminants	Separation method		Facilities	
	Estimated	Measured		Projected	Performed	Driver	Facility
$^{226}\text{Ra}(p,2n)^{225}\text{Ac}$		24[19] 90, 13, 7.1 [20]	Meas ^{226}Ac , ^{224}Ac ^{135}La , ^{140}La	-	Extraction chromatography	>14 MeV cyclotron	†
$^{226}\text{Ra}(\gamma,n)^{225}\text{Ra}$	0.77 ^{225}Ra [21]	0.55 [22]	-	-	ion exchange	30 MeV LINAC	‡
$^{\text{nat}}\text{Th}(\gamma, 3n)^{229}\text{Th}$	6×10^{-9} yr^{-1} [23]	-	-	^{229}Th gen.	-	High-I LINAC	ARIEL GELINA ...
$^{226}\text{Ra}(n,2n)^{225}\text{Ra}$	-	0.087, 0.091 [24]	^{223}Ra	-	Exchange chromatography	^2H accelerator	BNL
$^{230}\text{Th}(n,2n)^{229}\text{Th}$	$1.5 \times 10^{-3*}$ yr^{-1}	-	-	^{229}Th gen.		Fast n reactor	JOYO
$^{\text{nat}}\text{U}$, $^{\text{nat}}\text{Th}(p,X)^{225}\text{Ac}$, ^{225}Ra	0.25[JJF], 0.55[25] 0.29 [CDFI],		^{227}Ac		Radiochemistry, Mass separation	>70 MeV p accelerator	ISOL@ MYRRHA, MEDICIS, LANSCE, BLIP, TRIUMF

*Calculated yield rate for the JOYO reactor is normalised to GBq per gram target material per hour of irradiation in the reactor with the reactor's standard fast neutron flux.

†Any facility possessing a 14 MeV cyclotron, and with authorisation to handle GBq of ^{226}Ra .

‡Any facility possessing a 30 MeV electron LINAC, and with authorisation to handle GBq of ^{226}Ra

3.1 $^{226}\text{Ra}(p,2n)^{225}\text{Ac}$

This reaction was first presented in the literature in 2005 by Apostolidis et al [20]. The study found that the cross section reaches a maximum of 710 mb at an incident proton energy of 16.8 MeV, with a measured threshold energy of 8.8 MeV. The calculated threshold energy for this reaction is 6.8 MeV. The reaction is therefore accessible for most operational cyclotrons listed on the IAEA cyclotron database (<https://nucleus.iaea.org/sites/accelerators/Pages/Cyclotron.aspx>). One of the main issues in pursuing this method is the procurement of the target material ^{226}Ra . It is furthermore challenging to produce targets of relevant thickness for isotope production. Nonetheless, a patent was filed for the fabrication of such ^{226}Ra targets [26]. A major issue is the decay of ^{226}Ra to ^{222}Rn , a volatile radioactive gas which poses serious radio-protection concerns. One gram of ^{226}Ra target material has an activity of 1 Curie (37 GBq), therefore extreme care has to be taken.

Table 1 shows that this method has the greatest efficiency, i.e the greatest amount of ^{225}Ac can be produced when normalised to integrated beam intensity and amount of target material. However three major factors prevent large scale production at any given facility. Firstly, the radioactivity and the procurement difficulties of the target material are prohibitive to accumulating large targets. Furthermore, protons of the approximate 15 MeV energy required for this reaction are quickly stopped in Ra metal. At a distance of 0.7 mm, the energy lost by the protons is such that the proton energy is below the excitation threshold for the $^{226}\text{Ra}(p,2n)^{225}\text{Ac}$ reaction. This means that the thickness of targets in which the reaction can happen is fundamentally limited to this range, that limits isotope production potential. Finally, this high stopping power of the protons also limits the proton beam intensity due to the limited cooling abilities of such thin targets. Thus, only modest beam currents can be used. These considerations mean that no single facility will be able to perform large scale production of ^{225}Ac with this method.

3.2 $^{226}\text{Ra}(\gamma, n)^{225}\text{Ra}$

A photonuclear reaction pathway has also been proposed. In this pathway electrons of energy 20-30 MeV bombard a metal target. The resulting bremsstrahlung photons are then collimated and directed on ^{226}Ra target material. This reaction induces neutron evaporation of ^{226}Ra to generator ^{225}Ra . The ^{225}Ra is a generator for ^{225}Ac that can be eluted every 18 days. O.D. Maslov et al performed measurements with a 24 MeV maximal photon energy[22]. Their results suggest a ^{225}Ac yield of 550 Bq/($\mu\text{A h mg }^{226}\text{Ra}$). Such experiments requiring thin ^{226}Ra targets present the same procurement and radio protection challenges as previously. This reaction is less efficient than the previous but can be leveraged by facilities with electron linear accelerators (LINACs). Furthermore, the proton power deposition (and energy loss) in the target material is not a limiting factor for photonuclear reactions. Thus this reaction could be scaled to thicker ^{226}Ra targets.

3.3 $^{\text{nat}}\text{Th}(\gamma, 3n)^{229}\text{Th}$

Another method using photonuclear reactions is the production of the ^{229}Th generator from natural Thorium targets bombarded with 30-90 MeV electron beams[23]. The photon energy spectrum induces several nucleon evaporation reactions including at least two that have significant branching to ^{229}Th ($^{\text{nat}}\text{Th}(\gamma, 3n)^{229}\text{Th}$, $^{\text{nat}}\text{Th}(\gamma, n)(\gamma, n)(\gamma, n)^{229}\text{Th}$). This method has not yet been experimentally demonstrated, nor have the cross section estimations of TENDL upon which the report is based been determined through experiment. Nonetheless, the principle of producing ^{229}Th generators through this reaction is argued by the authors of the study to be important for global supply of ^{225}Ac . This is due to the longevity of the ^{229}Th generator. Furthermore, >30 MeV electron LINACs are operated in many laboratories worldwide, so this method could be an important pathway for a more democratic supply of ^{225}Ac .

3.4 $^{226}\text{Ra}(n,2n)^{225}\text{Ra}$

This method requires fast neutrons to induce a 2-neutron evaporation. The TENDL estimated cross section is above 2 b. Some targetry considerations are simplified by the fact that little energy is deposited by neutrons in the target. A proof of principle experiment was performed by J. Morell et al using deuteron break up on a thick Beryllium target as a source of energy-tunable neutrons[24]. The resulting neutron beam then irradiated a ^{226}Ra sample. It was suggested in this work that a 10g ^{226}Ra target irradiated with a 600 μA deuteron beam at 33 MeV for 5 days would produce 64 GBq of ^{225}Ac . This is based on the calculated production rate of 89 MBq/(mAh g ^{226}Ra) at 33 MeV. While novel, this method could leverage deuteron beam facilities. Furthermore, the method could be scaled to thicker ^{226}Ra targets if radioactive handling issues can be overcome due to low energy deposition of the neutrons in the material.

3.5 $^{230}\text{Th}(n,2n)^{229}\text{Th}$

The previous method that relies on an intense source of fast neutrons could also in theory be pursued in a fast nuclear reactor. Morell however predicts that the neutron intensity of such a method renders the production rate uncompetitive. On the other hand, fast neutron reactors could viably produce a ^{229}Th generator through the $^{230}\text{Th}(n,2n)^{229}\text{Th}$ reaction. This approach requires a long irradiation time to accumulate sufficient ^{229}Th . The advantage of this method is that it generates a sustainable stock of ^{229}Th that can be regularly eluted due to the long ^{229}Th half life of 7880 years. For example, the authors suggest a 10-year irradiation of ^{230}Th , which would yield a ^{229}Th source that can be eluted to contribute 6.5GBq ^{225}Ac per year. Another advantage of this method is the relative ease of procurement of ^{230}Th which can be extracted from pitchblende [27].

3.6 $^{\text{nat}}\text{U}, ^{\text{nat}}\text{Th}(p, X)^{225}\text{Ac}, ^{225}\text{Ra}$

Finally, the method of high energy (>70 MeV) proton spallation of uranium or thorium is considered. In such a method, high energy protons impinge on thick targets and induce many nuclear reactions, with channels leading to the production of thousands of nuclei. Cross sections have been measured for proton spallation of thorium at many beam energies of 70 - 200 MeV[28, 29]. Dedicated experiments also measured cross sections at 438 [30] and 800[25] MeV. Although no cross section has been measured for proton spallation of uranium, the yields of ^{225}Ac have been measured at online facilities such as ISOLDE or TRIUMF. This method has already been adopted relatively extensively as mentioned in section 2. Facilities such as BLIP, LANSCE (USA), TRIUMF (Canada) and the Institute for Nuclear research (Russia) have used this technique for the production of ^{225}Ac . Optimistic estimations of the annual production rate are given by Zhuikov et al and Griswold et al as hundreds of GBqs [29, 31]. While this method can produce high quantities of ^{225}Ac in relatively short irradiation times, there are a number of disadvantages. One is the infrastructure required. Few facilities in the world have access proton accelerators operating at energies greater than 70 MeV, therefore supply through this method will inevitably rely on the successful operation of such facilities. Furthermore, there are issues with the subsequent recovery of ^{225}Ac . So far, ^{225}Ac is primarily recovered through radiochemistry that offers no degree of isotopic selectivity. This is problematic as through the spallation reaction, contaminants ^{227}Ac and ^{226}Ac are co-produced. If no further mass or isotope selective step is performed, ^{225}Ac sources obtained through this method typically contain a contamination of ^{227}Ac of 0.15% by activity at end of irradiation. The impurity level is then generally given by Equation 1, with $t = t_{\text{irr}} + t_{\text{wait}}$.

$$\frac{A_{227}(t)}{A_{225}(t)} = \frac{\sigma_{227}(1 - e^{-\lambda_{227}t_{\text{irr}}})e^{-\lambda_{227}t_{\text{wait}}}}{\sigma_{225}(1 - e^{-\lambda_{225}t_{\text{irr}}})e^{-\lambda_{225}t_{\text{wait}}}} \quad (1)$$

Here, σ_X and λ_X are the cumulative cross section and radioactive decay constant, respectively, for the

Ac nuclide with mass number X. It is currently unclear whether this amount of ^{227}Ac can have adverse radiotoxic effects in patients. What is clear is that ^{227}Ac introduces extra radioactive contamination risks for any laboratory involved in further synthesis of ^{225}Ac . Furthermore, if ^{225}Ac -based radiopharmaceuticals without further isotopic purification are given to patients in hospitals, it is likely necessary to treat the patients' excreta as ^{227}Ac -containing radioactive material. This consideration generates an important and costly waste storage and disposal issue, due to the long 22 year half-life of ^{227}Ac .

In an attempt to address the contamination of collected ^{225}Ac with ^{227}Ac , isotopically selective separation is also actively pursued. For example, ^{225}Ac can be obtained from proton irradiated thorium- or uranium-based targets through the means of online or offline resonant laser ionization and mass separation. Mass separated ^{225}Ac has already been collected through implantation on foils both online at ISOLDE and TRIUMF, and offline at CERN MEDICIS. The ionization and mass separation step is costly in radioisotopic yield but hugely beneficial in radioisotopic purity. Technical details of what is demonstrably achievable with mass separation are given in section 4.

Despite the above mentioned difficulties with limited facilities and ^{227}Ac contamination, the method of high energy proton spallation of actinide targets remains extremely promising. Notably, this is because the production can be greatly scaled at a given facility. For example, thick stacks of thorium foils, or annealed ThO_2 pellets can be irradiated at once. The target material itself is much less radioactive than the ^{226}Ra , and the high energy protons have energy well above the excitation threshold even after passing through many centimetres of target material (especially at CERN ISOLDE where beam energies of >1 GeV are used). Thus the thin target limitations that apply to low energy proton irradiation of ^{226}Ra do not apply to high energy proton irradiation of thorium or uranium.

In the past, UC_x targets have been irradiated for the purpose of experimental production. The reason for this material choice is mostly due to its frequent use at ISOL facilities such as CERN ISOLDE or TRIUMF. Fluka calculations show that irradiation of a Th-based target yields a factor 20 more ^{225}Ac compared to a target with equivalent number density of $^{\text{nat}}\text{U}$ at end of irradiation. This is shown in figure 1. One sees in this figure a smaller activity in the top right hand region corresponding to the beginning of the actinide series. The exact choice of material composition (i.e. metal vs ceramic, microstructure considerations) depends on the separation modality to be employed. This question is explored in more detail in section 5.

4 Separation

Radioisotopes are produced in irradiated targets, but to be of medical use they must be separated from this environment efficiently and selectively. The most common technique for radioisotope separation comprises radiochemistry, but RIMS has also been used at facilities such as TRIUMF and MEDICIS. Different methods of each of these techniques can be applied to produce samples with different yields and purities. In section 4.1 the technique of radiochemistry will be described, with subsections

1. Radiochemical separation to recover the Ra fraction for use as $^{225}\text{Ra}/^{225}\text{Ac}$ generator (and valorisation of the eluted ^{225}Ac fraction as a ^{213}Bi generator).
2. Resonance laser ionisation and mass separation of ^{225}Ac from an irradiated target to recover ^{225}Ra from surface ionization and ^{225}Ac from a combination of surface and laser ionization.
3. Radiochemical separation to recover separate eluates of radium and actinium. This is followed by laser ionization and mass separation of the actinium fraction deposited as a salt on a suitable refractory metal substrate (e.g. rhenium). The recovered radium fraction is used as a $^{225}\text{Ra}/^{225}\text{Ac}$ generator.

Figure 1: A radionuclide inventory by activity per cubic centimeter immediately after a 29.8 hour irradiation with 1.4 GeV protons at $1\mu\text{A}$. The colourbar axis is normalised to the inverse of the relative number density of the target atoms in a given volume (U: $0.0156\text{ mol cm}^{-3}$, Th: $0.0467\text{ mol cm}^{-3}$) such that production cross sections can be compared between the materials. The ^{225}Ac activity density is 16800 kBq cm^{-3} and 361 kBq cm^{-3} for ThO₂ and UC_x respectively, while the respective ^{227}Ac activity densities are 28 kBq cm^{-3} and 0.378 kBq cm^{-3} .

A detailed discussion of each of these methods is included in the following section.

4.1 Radiochemical separation

Radiochemical separation of ^{225}Ac from irradiated targets is commonly performed. The bulk target material is separated from reaction products in a first step, and in a second step ^{225}Ac can be separated from other reaction products. An ideal radiochemical separation scheme would allow efficient recovery of the target material. It should also result in a solution containing the isotope of interest that can be further processed into a radiopharmaceutical (i.e. the pH should be matched to the subsequent chelation reaction and there should be few impurities with similar co-ordination number that would compete for chelator binding).

Radiochemical separation is an ideal solution when the production method does not result in the co-production of other long-lived isotopes of the element of interest. For example, it is used for recovering ^{225}Ac from irradiated ^{226}Ra targets where cross sections for ^{227}Ac production are negligible, due to the highly excited resultant ^{227}Ac nuclear state, which rapidly decays through (multiple) neutron emission. ^{226}Ac produced through the $^{226}\text{Ra}(p,n)^{226}\text{Ac}$ channel can be left to decay due to the relatively short . Furthermore, generator production of ^{225}Ac from ^{225}Ra or ^{229}Th is based on radiochemical methods which are applied to periodically extract ^{225}Ac while recovering the generator.

On the other hand, in irradiation scenarios such as the high energy proton spallation of natural uranium- or thorium-based targets, care must be taken as ^{227}Ac is co-produced in quantities significant enough to preclude medical use. It has been observed in radiochemical studies that ^{227}Ac remains in the Ac eluates with a fractional activity given by Equation 1. Therefore, isotopically selective methods must be applied if ^{227}Ac is to be avoided. One example exists in the literature of a way to radiochemically isolate ^{227}Ac -free ^{225}Ac [32]. In this method, the first actinium eluate ('first pass actinium') has the typical ^{227}Ac content of 0.15%. The research group collected the radium eluate separately from the first pass actinium

eluate. In the radium eluate, ^{225}Ac grows in through the radioactive decay of ^{225}Ra , where it reaches a maximum activity after 18 days. After this time, the collected radium eluate is passed through the exchange chromatography column to separate the actinium from the radium. The resulting actinium sample contained ^{227}Ac below the detection limit of the inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) sample measurement, corresponding to $7.5 \times 10^{-5}\%$ of the sample activity. While this method is elegant, the problem remains that the ‘first pass’ actinium cannot be immediately used as a ^{225}Ac source.

Radiochemical separation of ^{225}Ac from irradiated thorium targets has been documented by groups from TRIUMF, the Russian institute for nuclear research and the Tri-lab effort. In each case a combination of exchange and extraction chromatography are employed. The facilities and methods are broadly the same.

4.1.1 Method Outline

In the process of radiochemical separation, the goal is to obtain solutions of ^{225}Ac and ^{225}Ra with high radionuclidic purity. Early studies showed that with two chromatography steps, it was possible to recover a pure actinium fraction from the irradiated thorium matrix with a radiochemical yield $> 85\%$ [33, 34]. Later efforts demonstrated that a ^{225}Ra containing fraction could be independently collected using three columns, raising the prospect of obtaining a $^{225}\text{Ra}/^{225}\text{Ac}$ generator simultaneously from the processing of one thorium target stack [35]. Furthermore, such a method allows ^{223}Ra and ^{224}Ra to be isolated, which are also relevant for medical use. However, in this study the authors did not suggest how the Ra isotopes could be separated from one another. Another study showed that using a two step exchange and extraction chromatography setup, one could repeat the second step on the ^{225}Ra containing generator to obtain pure ^{225}Ac samples [32].

In each case, a process similar to that described in Figure 2. is followed. Note that the presence of stable impurities with similar co-ordination numbers to actinium will lead to competition during the chelation reaction. The labelling of the vector molecule with any stable contaminant reduces the molar activity of the final radiopharmaceutical product.

An analysis of the optimization of the radiochemistry steps is beyond the scope of the paper. An in-depth analysis of the optimization of the cation exchange step however was performed by Fitzsimmons et al. In this study the specific control parameters to ensure reliable and pure ^{225}Ac recovery with a radiochemical yield of $>90\%$ were defined [36].

Figure 2: A general schematic for a radiochemical separation procedure

4.1.2 Sample Characteristics

The resulting sample quality is determined by proton beam energy, irradiation time, target material purity, irradiated target cool down time, processing time, the selectivity and the bed volume of the exchange resins used in the chromatography step and the pH of the washes used for elution. As previously mentioned, two samples of ^{225}Ac are recovered from radiochemical separation. The so-called ‘first pass

actinium' sample has been found to contain the impurities shown in Figure 3 which was adapted from [32].

Table 1. Average ($n = 2$) Radionuclidic Purity of $^{227,225}\text{Ac}^\dagger$ and $^{225}\text{Ac}^*$ Products, Decay Corrected to the Times of Final Product Purification^a

	$t_{1/2}$	percent radioactivity [%]	
		$^{227,225}\text{Ac}^\dagger$	$^{225}\text{Ac}^*$
Ac-225	9.92 d	93.04	98.82
Ac-227	21.8 y	0.15	$<7.5 \times 10^{-5}$
Ac-226	29.4 h	5.83	<0.01
La-140	1.68 d	2.29	0.01
Ru-106	372 d	<0.04	0.13
Ru-103	39.2 d	0.25	0.72
Sr-85	64.8 d	0.14	0.33
Th-227	18.7 d	<0.04	<0.17
Ra-226	1600 y	<0.01	<0.06
Ra-225	14.9 d	<0.01	<0.05
Ra-224	3.66 d	<0.07	<0.02
Ra-223	11.4 d	<0.04	<0.14
Ce-141	32.5 d	<0.01	<0.03
Ba-140	12.8 d	<0.01	<0.04

^a ^{227}Ac values were determined by ICP- MS (Section S6), while all other values were determined by gamma spectroscopy (Section S3). The percent radioactivity does not include nuclides (ex. $^{89,90}\text{Sr}$) that are not detectable by gamma spectroscopy.

Figure 3: Activities of impurities relative to ^{225}Ac samples measured by gamma spectroscopy. Table adapted from [32]

Lack of isotopic selectivity notably results in a ^{227}Ac contamination with a ratio given by Equation 1. The ^{227}Ac activity fraction in a first pass actinium sample was measured by Robertson et al. to be $(0.15 \pm 0.04)\%$ with correction for radioactive decay. This is broadly consistent with the ratio of 0.17% produced in ThO_2 , predicted by a CERN FLUKA simulation for a 27 hour irradiation with 1.78×10^{17} 1.4 GeV protons. In each of these cases, the level of contaminant ^{227}Ac activity prohibits use of the recovered ^{225}Ac sample for medical purposes according to clinical opinion [37].

In so-called 'second pass' Actinium, the sample has the radioactive impurities summarised in the final column of the table in Figure 3. The ^{225}Ac content is suppressed beyond the detection limit of the ICP-MS system used. However, the resulting Activity of the ^{225}Ac produced here relies on feeding from the ^{225}Ra which is produced at a cross section that is approximately 6.2 times lower than direct ^{225}Ac production. If this generator is optimally eluted every 18 days, then ^{225}Ac activities equal to 43%, 18% and 8% of the initial ^{225}Ra activity can be recovered.

4.2 Mass separation

As outlined in the list of section 4, there are two ways in which mass separation can be employed for collecting pure samples of ^{225}Ac from irradiated thorium- or uranium-based targets. The first is applying the technique directly to the irradiated target. The second is applying the technique to essentially the 'first pass actinium' that is deposited on some inert substrate.

Each of these methods requires the same facilities and setup, however the quality and efficiency of the collection may greatly vary. The following sections will outline the general method as well as the expected differences between the two techniques.

4.2.1 Facilities required

In order to perform mass separation, a mass separator is naturally required. There are different types of mass separator whose performance is characterised by their mass resolving power. Another key feature of the mass separation process is the ionization process used. Experiments have been performed at CERN with a hot cavity laser ion source to ionize atomic actinium as well as a versatile arc discharge ion source (VADIS) to ionise molecular actinium. During the experiments employing a hot cavity laser ionization source, it was observed that the surface ionization mechanism alone ionized an insufficient fraction of ^{225}Ac , and that the laser enhancement was imperative to perform a successful collection. Therefore in order to perform this method, a laboratory equipped with the means to provide laser beams for efficient stepwise resonant ionization is required. Figure Aside from laser ionisation, a versatile arc discharge ion source with a calibrated fluorine leak has been employed online at CERN ISOLDE to produce $^{225}\text{AcF}_x$ with an irradiated UC_x target. This method is considered as an alternative to the laser ion source used previously for ^{225}Ac collections at CERN MEDICIS. A proposal to perform a systematic comparison between the two ion sources at CERN MEDICIS has been submitted.

An overview of the key requirements for operating a mass separator is given in Fig. 4

Figure 4: The key requirements for operating a mass separator

4.2.2 Method Outline

A source of ^{225}Ac , (irradiated target, or ^{225}Ac deposited on substrate), is loaded into the target oven on the ‘front end’ of a mass separator. The oven is heated to vaporise the materials inside. This vapor effuses to the ion source, where atoms of ^{225}Ac and other species are ionized. These ions are accelerated across an electrostatic potential difference between the ion source high voltage platform and a grounded extraction electrode. The resulting ion beam is then shaped and focused using on beam optics such as an Einzel lens and electrostatic deflectors. It subsequently traverses a field free region before reaching the mass separator, where the beam is separated into its constituents by mass. Finally, the beam corresponding to a specific mass can be implanted on a collection foil downstream.

The higher the mass resolution of a mass separator, the better spatially confined each constituent mass is at the separator’s focal plane. For the mass separator used at CERN MEDICIS, (Mass resolving power = 500), isobars cannot be separated. Therefore, beam constituents of the same atomic number (i.e. ^{225}Ra and ^{225}Ac for $A = 225$) are co-selected and subsequently implanted. Isotopes of neighbouring masses are in principal well separated by a magnet with resolving power = 500, however some ions of

neighbouring masses may pass through the colimator and be implanted in the foil, due to the extended spatial distribution of the ion beam. Conversely, some ions of the mass of interest may be blocked by the colimator. This effect is worse for larger masses, as the FWHM gets larger, and the spatial separation between beams of adjacent masses is smaller as shown in Figure 5a. For a given mass, the separation factor can be calculated as a function of the mass resolving power of the separator (the ratio of the fraction of the isotope of interest collected to the fraction of the isotope of an adjacent mass on the collection foil). This is shown for mass 225 in Figure 5b. At MEDICIS, this means that ^{227}Ac would be suppressed by a factor of approximately 40. Note that this is a worst case scenario estimate, assuming that the mass peaks are shaped like Lorentzians. In reality, preliminary results show that a factor 6000 separation was achieved for ^{227}Ac from ^{225}Ac at CERN MEDICIS.

Figure 5: Simple calculations of magnet performance assuming Lorentzian mass peak profiles, and using measurements taken from [38]

4.2.3 Sample characteristics

Three experiments have been performed at CERN MEDICIS during which ^{225}Ac has been collected. Two of these experiments concern the separation of pure ^{225}Ac deposited on rhenium foil, and a ThO_2 felt respectively. The third experiment was performed to separate and collect ^{225}Ac from an irradiated ThO_2 target.

In the first two experiments, it was concluded that the separation efficiency was upwards of 10%, with the laser ionization efficiency being the limiting factor.

In the latter experiment, a lower collection efficiency was achieved, due to the high temperature requirements of the target oven for ^{225}Ac release, as well as a diminished laser ionization efficiency that can be attributed to ion load effects.

The collection efficiency for ^{225}Ac was estimated to be 4 %. The total activity of ^{227}Ac in the sample was 0.063(5) Bq. There was also found to be progeny of ^{226}Ra in the sample. No measurement was performed to assess stable impurities. By comparing this to FLUKA simulations of the radionuclide inventory at the start of collection, the overall separation factor for ^{227}Ac versus ^{225}Ac , was approx. 6000. This method allows ^{225}Ac to be collected with relatively low efficiency, but suppresses ^{227}Ac far below the aforementioned maximum desirable ratio of 0.01%. The additional ^{226}Ra leads to daughter nuclei with high energy γ rays, thus the ^{225}Ac samples produced by this method require a further chemical purification step to separate ^{226}Ra from ^{225}Ac .

The conclusions of these studies are that ^{227}Ac is sufficiently suppressed from ^{225}Ac making it suitable

for medical use. However a radiochemical separation step to isolate ^{225}Ac from possible Ra contaminants should be performed on the collected sample.

4.2.4 Purified source versus irradiated target

Performing laser ionization and mass separation on an irradiated target has been shown to be less efficient than performing the same process on a ‘pure’ source. This can be explained as follows.

Firstly, the isotope of interest is created by nuclear reaction directly in the target material grains. It must therefore diffuse into the target microstructure before effusing into the ion source cavity. On the other hand, if the isotope of interest is deposited on an inert and thermally stable material, it only needs to desorb from the surface, which requires a lower temperature.

Secondly, irradiated targets contain much more material, including (radioactive) isotopes of many elements, as shown in Figure 1. In this case, two major problems are encountered. The first is that the target must first be outgassed before a collection can begin, typically for a couple of days, in order to avoid pressure spikes while heating the target to the onset of release temperature of Actinium. During this time, a negligible amount of actinium is released from the target, and a fraction $e^{-\lambda_{225}t_{outgas}}$ is lost to decay. The second problem is that even after outgassing has occurred and the oven is heated to higher temperature to promote actinium release, many contaminant species, (mostly stable impurities, but some radioactive species) are released too. The released species with low ionization potentials (typically alkali metals or alkali earth metals) become surface ionized in the ion source. This generates space charge that perturbs the extraction field and reduces the extraction efficiency of laser ions drastically. Experiments performed show that this effect becomes important at total beam currents of above 100 nA, which is easily reached when performing a collection of an irradiated target. As a consequence, much of the Actinium is simply lost through a low ion extraction efficiency. In the studies performed at CERN MEDICIS, it has been shown that the laser ionization efficiency of ^{225}Ac was approximately three times lower for the irradiated target compared to a pure source.

On the other hand, performing a collection of actinium directly from an irradiated target has some benefits over the use of a chemically purified sample as the source. Firstly, the target can simply be re-irradiated after the collection has been performed and no further processing is required. This can be repeated many times until the target material sinters due to repeated heating cycles, or the target container’s conductivity decreases due to material fractures. This also avoids the involved radiochemical processing of the activated target material which must be performed in a hot cell. Secondly, other isotopes can be collected in parallel. For example, by controlling the temperature of the target or transfer line, ^{225}Ra could be collected first before ^{225}Ac . Furthermore, ^{227}Ac could also be collected if a double-slit system is used in the mass separator and then used as a generator for ^{223}Ra . Nonetheless, it is clear that the collection efficiency for chemically purified ^{225}Ac is more efficient than for ^{225}Ac from an irradiated target.

5 Ideal separation approach for spallation produced ^{225}Ac

In light of the above discussion, an schematic summary of the three possible separation methods is given in figure 6.

It is that the separation method that yields the most directly usable ^{225}Ac is the two step process composed of radiochemical separation followed by resonant laser ionization and mass separation. In this way, the ‘second pass’ ^{225}Ac is efficiently recovered from pure radiochemical methods. It also valorizes the ‘first pass’ ^{225}Ac by greatly suppressing the ^{227}Ac content with resonant laser ionization and mass separation.

While the efficiency and purity has been considered in this calculation, the cost of target reprocessing for

Figure 6: An illustrative example of the three separation procedures applied to an irradiated target with 10 MBq of ^{225}Ac and 1.6 MBq of ^{225}Ra . Decay losses during processing outside the mass separation steps are not accounted for. The efficiencies quoted are based from work by Robertson et al.[32] and work by Johnson et al.[39]. The bottom values are the recovered ^{225}Ra or ^{225}Ac activities. Yes/No refers to whether the recovered sample is suitable for medical use.

the cases in which radiochemistry is performed has not. The recovery of thorium metal from ThO_2 is well documented [40]. On the other hand the fraction of ThO_2 precipitate that can be recovered following radiochemistry is not documented. More research is needed to be able to tell whether this recovered ThO_2 must be reprocessed at the nuclear facility or whether it can be outsourced, which depends on the activity of impurities in the recovered ThO_2 .

It may be that the dissolution and reprocessing of thorium foil targets is more cost effective than the fabrication of dedicated ISOL-type thorium-based targets that would be used and reused for pure mass separation. Here, the grain size and open porosity have to be well-controlled, which require specialized annealing techniques. Furthermore, the pH of thorium products has to be controlled such as to avoid pyrogenic effects.

Since the production and separation of ^{225}Ac is a very active area of research, it is worth considering whether any future developments may change the conclusions drawn from the illustrative example in this section.

The current limitation of radiochemical separation is the saturation of the N,N,N',N' tetraoctyl-diglycolamide (DGA) column used in extraction chromatography by stable impurities when processing an irradiated thorium target. This is what reduced the efficiency from 98% to 44% in the recovery of ^{225}Ac . The authors of this study suggest improvements to their method including changing column volume and using purer target materials. It is therefore likely that the radiochemical yield of 'first pass' actinium could be improved. In any case, this can only be valorized as an ^{225}Ac source by further mass separation. Hence, the conclusion that radiochemical separation followed by mass separation is the most efficient becomes even stronger. On the other hand, if it is shown in the future that ^{213}Bi is just an effective a TAT agent as ^{225}Ac then it could be considered that pure radiochemical separation is most efficient (as ^{227}Ac contamination does not significantly impact the recovered ^{213}Bi purity).

With respect to the pure mass separation, there are ongoing developments that could increase the efficiency of this process. The first is related to the use of the resonant laser ionisation of ^{225}Ac . A more

efficient laser ionization scheme might exist for actinium, which would increase the collection efficiency. Furthermore, research into new specialized high-throughput ion sources is ongoing. Indeed, the current ion sources used at CERN MEDICIS are optimised for rapid extraction of ions for the study of short lived isotopes. In the case of medical radio-isotope production, efficient extraction is sought more than rapid extraction. The ion source body geometry itself could be changed to increase laser-atom interaction probability and to reduce recombination effects. Furthermore, materials with lower work function than rhenium, such as tungsten, tantalum, or ceramics[41]), could be used to reduce surface ionization efficiency such that the ion current of contaminants is reduced, which is known to negatively impact laser ionization efficiency. This must be investigated to determine the effect on laser enhancement and overall ionization efficiency. Aside from the developments of the laser ion source, there is also the prospect of creating actinium molecules, then using a versatile arc discharge and laser ion source (VAD(L)IS) for ionization. Here, a halogen gas leak is injected into the target oven, such that the species within react with it and volatilize. Then, the molecular species effuse to the ion source, where ionization by electron bombardment (VADIS) and/or laser ionization can occur. The resulting molecular ions are then extracted and the mass separator is set such that the central beam corresponds to most intense molecular ion. At higher mass beams, the mass resolution decreases thus it could be expected that in such a scenario, the total separation factor between ^{225}Ac and ^{227}Ac would be worse. However, since laser ionization and mass separation suppresses the ^{227}Ac orders of magnitude below the exemption limit per patient dose, a compromise here is of little cost. If there is a factor three increase in the efficiency with VAD(L)IS, then the two methods of radiochemical separation followed by mass separation, and pure mass separation would again need to be reviewed to decide which is most beneficial to pursue.

6 Outlook

It has been shown through this review that the most efficient way to produce ^{225}Ac is through proton irradiation of ^{226}Ra targets. At the same time, the method which has the greatest scaling potential is the one using high energy proton spallation of uranium- or thorium-based targets. Approaches to produce more ^{229}Th are also considered useful to accumulate quasi-permanent generators which can be reliably and periodically eluted, as is currently done for most worldwide ^{225}Ac supply.

Due to the high radiosotopic purity of ^{225}Ac in irradiated ^{226}Ra targets, it is best recovered by radiochemical methods. In this way, a high radiochemical yield is ensured and the resulting ^{225}Ac is produced efficiently and purely.

In high energy proton-irradiated thorium- or uranium-based targets, a provisional optimized separation method is proposed. Firstly, the bulk target material should be precipitated. Secondly, a combination of exchange and extraction chromatography should be applied to the solution in order to obtain 'first pass ^{225}Ac ' (^{227}Ac contaminated ^{225}Ac), as well as a $^{225}\text{Ra}/^{225}\text{Ac}$ generator. The generator should be eluted to periodically obtain ^{225}Ac . Offline mass separation should then be applied to the 'first pass' sample. The optimal choice of ion source, as well as a set of optimized operational parameters is still under investigation.

The quantity of ^{225}Ac that can be produced worldwide depends on operating constraints and capabilities of facilities. It is of the authors opinion that a worldwide collaborative effort to leverage a combination of existing and emerging technologies should be established in order to support a global production chain that can reliably supply to oncology research community. This would become ever more important as demand for this promising isotope continues to grow.

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